

DIAQUO-MONO-OXALATO-ANTIMONY COMPLEX

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Aquo-hydroxo-mono-oxalato-antimony complex (A), which loses the molecule of water at 110° to 120°, but not over sulphuric acid, has been prepared. From the solubility of this complex at 35° in partially neutralised oxalic acid solution of various concentrations and p_H , the above complex has been found to react with a hydrogen ion, furnishing SbI_3 , which further reacts with an oxalate ion affording dioxalato-antimonite complex. The equilibrium constants of both the reactions have been determined.

Oxalate ion has been found to be removed to the solid phase when antimony oxide is kept in contact with a solution of less than 50% neutralised oxalic acid. This phenomenon is not observed with a solution containing more than 50% neutralised oxalic acid (Nanda and Pani, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 588). The system at lower p_H containing less than 50% neutralised oxalic acid has been investigated. The removal of oxalate from the solution to the solid phase is a clear indication of the formation of an insoluble oxalate compound of antimony. The amount of oxalate removed from the solution depends on the p_H of the solution, but the amount of antimony oxide added being indefinite, the solid phase has no stoichiometric composition. The composition of the solid phase therefore varies with the solid antimony oxide added. It becomes thus difficult to study the system containing two solid phases in equilibrium with the solution. It was therefore thought proper to prepare the insoluble compound first and study its properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were of Analar quality. Freshly prepared antimony oxide was refluxed with a concentrated solution of oxalic acid. The crystalline substance obtained was filtered, washed and dried at 110-20°. It was analysed for antimony content by standard potassium bromate, and antimony together with oxalate content, by standard potassium permanganate. The compound contains 53.59% Sb and 38.75% oxalate [calc. 53.69% and 38.82% respectively for $[Sb(OH)C_2O_4]$]. The same compound is also obtained by treating a solution of tartar emetic with a solution of oxalic acid. A hydrated compound

containing one molecule of water of crystallisation was obtained by dissolving a small amount of oxalic acid in a saturated aqueous solution of antimony chloride and heating gently to remove HCl. The compound was precipitated by adding ether in which antimony chloride and even saturated aqueous solution of antimony chloride were soluble. The compound was washed with ether and dried over H_2SO_4 in vacuum. It is free from chloride and contains 49.83% Sb and 35.89% $C_2O_4^{2-}$ (calc. 49.74% and 35.96% respectively for $SbOH.C_2O_4, H_2O$). The same compound can also be obtained by the first two methods provided that the samples are dried over H_2SO_4 and not at 110° to 120°. The water molecule most probably is present in the co-ordination sphere

and the compound is mono-aquo-monohydroxo-inono-oxalato-antimony complex. In a number of antimony complexes studied here, the co-ordination number of the antimony has been reported to be 4.

Several four-co-ordination solid antimony complexes have also been prepared (unpublished). It has been reported that the co-ordination number of antimony (CsSb_2F_7) is 4 (Bystrom and Wilhelmi, *Arkiv Kemi*, 1951, 3, 373).

All these are in favour of the assumption that the $\text{Sb}(\text{OH})\cdot\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ is a four-co-ordination complex. The compound is almost insoluble in water, but is slowly hydrolysed to antimony oxide and oxalic acid. The solubility in oxalic acid is also very small, but the solubility increases in partially neutralised oxalic acid. The compound was added to a 25% neutralised oxalic acid of known concentration and shaken in an electric shaker; when the equilibrium was reached, the oxalate content and antimony content were determined as before. It was found that the increase in oxalate content in g. moles in the solution was equal to the g. atoms of antimony in the solution. It is therefore concluded that the compound is not hydrolysed in oxalate solution and the solid phase, remaining in equilibrium with partially neutralised oxalic acid, is hydrated antimonyl oxalate, $\text{HO}\cdot\text{Sb}\cdot\text{C}_2\text{O}_4\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The solubility of antimonyl oxalate in partially neutralised oxalic acid solution of various concentrations at 35° and the p_H are recorded in Table I. The concentrations are expressed as [X] which indicates g. moles of X per litre.

TABLE I

Neutralisation.	[OX].	p_H .	[Sb] $\times 10^3$.	[HC ₂ O ₄ ⁻].	[Sbr] $\times 10^4$.	[Sbn] $\times 10^3$.	$K_1 \times 10^3$.
10%	0.2708	1.40	3.21	0.1581			
	0.2407	1.42	2.93	0.1427			
	0.2106	1.44	2.66	0.1270			
	0.1854	1.48	2.38	0.1162			
	0.1505	1.53	2.11	0.09797			
	0.1204	1.59	1.82	0.08175			
20%	0.2708	1.50	4.53	0.1716	5.218	4.008	2.34
	0.2407	1.61	3.77	0.1692	3.780	3.392	2.01
	0.2106	1.67	3.35	0.1481	3.528	2.997	2.02
	0.1854	2.76	3.03	0.1401	2.867	2.743	1.96
	0.1505	1.82	2.81	0.1168	2.498	2.570	2.20
	0.1204	1.92	2.24	0.09699	2.077	2.032	2.10
30%	0.2708	1.55	5.99	0.1775	4.650	5.525	3.11
	0.2407	1.65	5.03	0.1693	3.694	4.661	2.74
	0.2106	1.68	4.51	0.1521	3.447	4.165	2.73
	0.1854	1.77	3.89	0.1401	2.872	3.608	2.58
	0.1505	1.88	3.17	0.1188	2.278	2.942	2.48
	0.1204	1.96	2.57	0.0930	1.809	2.389	2.41
0%	0.2708	2.06	10.28	0.2261	1.4370	10.140	4.48
	0.2407	2.10	8.98	0.2035	1.3110	8.849	4.35
	0.2106	2.23	7.48	0.1843	0.9715	7.385	4.00
	0.1854	2.29	5.81	0.1649	0.8463	5.725	3.64
	0.1505	2.48	4.66	0.1362	0.6569	4.594	3.37
	0.1204	2.53	3.77	0.1109	0.4870	3.721	3.35

At the first sight the results appear to indicate that the solubility increases with increasing p_n (increasing neutralisation of oxalic acid). The results of each set, however, indicate that the maximum solubility in that set is observed in the solution in which the p_n is maximum. The solubility is therefore controlled by two factors, namely, hydrogen ion and oxalate ion.

Antimonyl oxalate is formed when antimony oxide is in contact with oxalic acid solution; a species of antimonyl oxalate (containing one oxalate per atom of antimony) evidently exists in solution. The soluble species, however, cannot be $\text{Sb.OH.C}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ since the increase in its solubility with increasing concentration of oxalate ion cannot be explained. The antimonyl oxalate therefore goes into solution either as a cationic (equation 1) or anionic complex (equation 2).

Hydrated antimony oxalate is therefore very similar to antimonious acid and the reactions (1) and (2) are very similar to the basic and acidic dissociation of antimonious acid (hydrated antimony oxide), as proposed in an earlier communication (Nanda and Pani, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 525).

If reaction (1) is assumed to be taking place, the concentration of the mono-oxalato cationic complex would be small at higher p_n .

If reaction (2) is assumed to be taking place, the concentration of the anionic complex in solution would increase with p_n , and in 50% or more neutralised oxalic acid solution, a significant amount of antimony would exist as anionic mono-oxalato complex. This is, however, not observed. The complex in such medium is dioxalato complex. It is therefore very probable that mono-oxalato complex, if at all exists, would be the cationic rather than the anionic one. The other reaction taking place would be the formation of the dioxalato complex by the interaction of the antimonyl oxalate with bioxalate ion.

The formation of the dioxalato complex would increase with increasing neutralisation of oxalic acid. The equilibrium constants of the reactions (1) and (3) are given by equation (1-1) and (3-1) respectively.

$$\frac{[\text{Sb}_r]}{[\text{H}^+]} = K \quad \dots (1-1)$$

$$\frac{[\text{Sb}_r]}{[\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4^-]} = K_1 \quad (3-1)$$

$[Sb_1]$, $[Sb_{II}]$, $[H^+]$ and $[HC_2O_4^-]$ represent respectively the molar concentration of the mono-oxalato cationic complex, dioxalato complex, hydrogen ion and bioxalate ion. Since both the reactions would take place, it is difficult to calculate K and K_1 . It can, however, be calculated as follows. Let $[Sb]$ be the total antimony in the solution. Hence,

$$[Sb] = [Sb_1] + [Sb_{II}] \quad \dots (4)$$

Substituting the value of $[Sb_1]$ from equation (1-1) and that of $[Sb_{II}]$ from equation (3-1) in equation (4), one gets

$$[Sb] = K [H^+] + K_1 [HC_2O_4^-]$$

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{[Sb]}{[H^+]} = K + K_1 \frac{[HC_2O_4^-]}{[H^+]} \quad \dots (4-1)$$

If $[Sb]/[H^+]$ is plotted against $[HC_2O_4^-]/[H^+]$, a straight line would be obtained, the slope of which would give K_1 and the intercept, K .

The concentration of bioxalate ion can be obtained as follows. The total oxalate in the solution is equal to the sum of the concentrations of that of originally taken $[OX]$ and the oxalate brought to the solution due the dissolution of antimonyl oxalate. Total oxalate = $[OX] + [Sb]$. Total oxalate in the solution is partly present in mono-oxalato complex Sb_1 , partly in dioxalato complex Sb_{II} , and the rest as free oxalic acid, bioxalate ion and oxalate ion. Hence,

$$[OX] + [Sb] = [Sb_1] + 2[Sb_{II}] + [H_2C_2O_4] + [HC_2O_4^-] + [C_2O_4^{2-}] \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{Since} \quad [Sb_1] + [Sb_{II}] = [Sb],$$

$$\begin{aligned} [OX] - [Sb_{II}] &= [H_2C_2O_4] + [HC_2O_4^-] + [C_2O_4^{2-}] \\ &= [HC_2O_4^-] \frac{[H^+]}{k_1} + [HC_2O_4^-] + \frac{k_2}{[H^+]} \cdot [HC_2O_4^-] \end{aligned}$$

where k_1 and k_2 are respectively the first and the second dissociation constant of oxalic acid ($k_1 = 5.7 \times 10^{-2}$, $k_2 = 6.9 \times 10^{-5}$; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1920, **86**, 381).

$$[HC_2O_4^-] = \frac{[OX] - [Sb_{II}]}{\frac{[H^+]}{k_1} + 1 + \frac{k_2}{[H^+]}} = \frac{[OX] - [Sb_{II}]}{a} \quad \dots (5-1)$$

The concentration of bioxalate ion can be calculated if $[Sb_{II}]$ is known. When the concentration of Sb_{II} is very small and most of the antimony exists as Sb_1 ,

$$[HC_2O_4^-]_1 = \frac{[OX]}{a} \quad \dots (5-2)$$

When the concentration of Sb_1 is very small and most of the complex is dioxalato complex Sb_{II} ,

$$[HC_2O_4^-]_2 = \frac{[OX] - [Sb]}{a} \quad \dots (5-3)$$

$[\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4^-]_1$ and $[\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4^-]_2$ for the 10% neutralised series were calculated. Since $[\text{Sb}]$ is small compared to $[\text{OX}]$ in this series, the difference between $[\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4^-]_1$ and $[\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4^-]_2$ is very small. The actual concentration of HC_2O_4^- would not be much different from these values. Assuming $[\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4^-]_2$ to be very nearly equal to $[\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4^-]$, $[\text{Sb}]/[\text{H}^+]$ was plotted against the corresponding $[\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4^-]/[\text{H}^+]$. Very nearly a straight line was obtained (out of six points four were on the straight line and two deviated a little). The value of K obtained from the intercept is 1.65×10^{-2} . Using this value of K , the concentration of Sb_1 was calculated by equation (1-1). $[\text{Sb}_1]$ was obtained by subtracting $[\text{Sb}_2]$ from $[\text{Sb}]$. The concentration of bioxalate ion was calculated by equation (5-1). The value K_1 calculated are shown in Table I. The mean value is 2.88×10^{-2} . The value of K_1 obtained from the slope of the straight line obtained with 10% neutralised series is 1.6×10^{-2} is not much different from the above mean value.

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